

High Energy Quantum Bound States and Classical Physics

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The classical limit of quantum mechanics is often considered in terms of the time dependent Schrodinger equation. In this note we consider the bound case solution i.e. a time dependence of $\exp(-iEt)$ and as in previous notes argue that time has been removed from this statistical equilibrium picture as a the quantum particle tries to establish a kind of impulse potential field based on superpositions of $\exp(ipx)$ terms. Such a potential field is linked with a bound state and does not involve following the particle about in time as it undergoes stochastic impulse hits with $\exp(ikx)$ terms from $V(x)=\text{Sum over } k \text{ } V_k \exp(ikx)$. On average a classical energy balance equation $KE(x)+V(x) = E_n$ holds for every energy E_n , but the average is created by a spread of momenta i.e. $W(x)=\text{wavefunction} = \text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx)$.

In this note we consider the case of a particle in an infinite potential well and note how the spatial resolution becomes very high at the same time that the momentum spread becomes very narrow in the case of high n (energy level). Thus as n becomes approaches infinite, it is not just the $v_{rms}(x)$ which is linked with x , but the statistical scenario of quantum mechanics approaches a situation in which x is being resolved to a very high level and p is almost constant. Furthermore quantum entropy becomes a constant (independent of n) as $n \rightarrow$ infinite suggesting a theory which is nonstatistical in this limit. This would represent a classical picture except for the fact that time is still removed from the quantum bound state i.e. forward and backward $\exp(ipx)$, $\exp(-ipx)$ still interfere. Given that x and p are well resolved locally for high n it seems one may follow the high n quantum particle in space and time and manually remove the forward and backward portions to create a theory of a particle moving in one direction under $V(x)$ i.e. classical physics. This bypasses the idea of a wavepacket whose x -spread increases in time and allows one to base classical physics on a bound state solution of a quantum particle in an infinite well.

Quantum Particle in an Infinite Well Potential

Classical physics is sometimes said to follow from limiting/averaging cases of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. In general, a wavepacket is formed which is localized in space but this packet $[\text{Sum over } p \text{ } a(p)\exp(ipx-iE(p)t)]$ carries many $\exp(-iE(p)t)$ terms which leads to a spatial spread which increases in time contrary to the behaviour of a classical particle.

In this note we argue that there seems to be no reason why a bound quantum state at high energy should not demonstrate classical behaviour without the use of a wavepacket. In particular the envelope of the quantum density $W^*(x)W(x)$ has been compared in the literature (1) to the classical bound density $C/v(x)$ where $v(x)$ is classical velocity. The classical density is linked to a system in which a particle moves first to the right in time and then to the left and it seems that one should be able to see this from a high n bound particle in an infinite potential which should signs of classical physics without the use of a time dependent Schrodinger equation involving a mix of energies $E(p)$.

Impulse Scenario

We argue that classical physics is an approximate theory based on a statistical picture of impulse hits. To establish this statistical picture, equilibrium is used which involves an averaging of particles moving forward and backwards. Unlike classical statistical mechanics a quantum particle with momentum p is physically associated with a nonlocal length, the wavelength proportional to $1/p$ and a probability density of $\exp(ipx)$. Thus nonlocality is an intrinsic property of quantum mechanics as are complex probabilities because a quantum particle in equilibrium does not follow a time reversal balance of collisions in and out of each momentum state p as it does in a Maxwell-Boltzmann gas. In other words, the physical scenario of a quantum particle receiving stochastic impulse hits from a potential $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$ such that $P(p_1)P(p_2) = P(p_1+p_2)$ i.e. $\exp(ipx) = P(p)$, is very different from the classical physics scenario.

It is interesting that for any quantum energy E_n , however, average energies obey a classical scenario i.e. $E_n = KE(x) + V(x)$ where $KE(x) = [-1/2m d/dx dW/dx]/W = KE(x)$ classical. The quantum particle, however, receives stochastic impulse hits which together with its nonlocal wavelength make the scenario anything but classical despite the fact that $v_{rms}(x)$ is classical. Furthermore there is a spatial density $W^*(x)W(x)$ which is quite different from a classical bound spatial density of $C/v(x)$ although at high n similarities appear (if one uses the envelope of the quantum density).

We have argued in previous notes that for a bound state, $\exp(-iEnt)$ indicates that time has been completely removed from the problem. It may be noted that $\exp(-iEnt)$ allows for $\exp(-iEnt)W_n(x)$ to be a solution of the time-dependent Schrodinger equation, but with time essentially absent. We thus argue that a bound particle establishes a kind of impulse potential field itself which is in equilibrium with the $V_k \exp(ikx)$ field of the potential $V(x)$. This resonance result does not depend on time and the momentum identity of the quantum particle continually changes. We further argue that this statistical equilibrium type picture should give insight into classical physics without resort to an equation which follows the quantum particle as $x(t)$ in some kind of classical limit.

Particle in an Infinite Potential Well

We consider a quantum particle in an infinite potential well as an example closely related to classical physics as there is no tunnelling. A set of $\exp(ipx)$ (p continuous) create a wavefunction $W(x)$ which is 0 outside the $[0, L]$ box and (2)

$$W(x) = \sqrt{2/L} \sin(2 \cdot 3.14 n/L x) \quad \text{inside the box.} \quad ((1))$$

$$\text{The momentum wavefunction is: } a(p) = (L / (3.14 \hbar)) [3.14n / (3.14n + pL)]^2 \text{ sinc}[(.5)(n \cdot 3.14 - pL)] \quad ((2))$$

One may note that for high n , ((1)) leads to very sharp local spatial resolution while ((2)) becomes almost like a delta function at $p = 3.14n/L$. In other words there is sharp position recognition at the same time that there is a very small momentum spread i.e. a unique momentum is almost present. This almost represents a classical scenario even though time is still removed from the quantum picture. It is no longer $\psi(x)$ which is known at each x and behaves classically, but the wavefunction suggests an almost single p value involved in impulse hits and this p value is high so that space is sharply resolved. In such a case:

$\sin(kn x)$ where $kn = 3.14 n/L$ where kn is usually an average value, one now has the situation where kn is almost a unique p value and:

$$\sin(kn x) = \frac{1}{2i} (\exp(ikn x) - \exp(-i kn x)) \quad ((3))$$

This now appears as a superposition of free particle wavefunctions (forwards and backwards motion) within $[0, L]$ and is no longer thought of as the superposition of many different momenta. $\exp(ikn x)$ and $\exp(-ikn x)$ should occur at different times i.e. the quantum picture is obscuring the motion now which is really forward with a fixed p and sharp x resolution in time and then backwards in a separate interval of time. This obscuring can, however, be performed for a classical bound particle by stating that spatial density is $C/v(x)$ without worrying whether the particle is moving in the forward or backwards direction.

Thus we argue that one may deduce classical motion from high n bound state quantum solutions of a particle in a well. In such a scenario, a set of momenta close to p are involved, but one uses one value of $\exp(-iE_n(p)t)$ and not a set as in a wavepacket.

As a result we argue that given the statistical nature of a quantum bound system, classical physics i.e. motion in one direction in time followed by motion in the opposite direction in another interval of time must be pulled out of the "timeless" bound state high n quantum solution. In such an approach, one does not have to follow the evolution of a quasi-classical wavefunction in time.

Uncertainty Principle

The momentum-space uncertainty principle states that:

$$\text{Standard deviation}(p) \text{ standard deviation}(x) \geq \hbar/2 \quad ((4))$$

This is often described in the following way: One cannot know the momentum and position of a quantum particle sharply at the same time. One may note, however, that ((4)) is a global condition as the spatial variance is calculated by integrating over all of space. Furthermore ((4)) is used to prove that the ground state cannot have zero energy by using the global value L as Δx . We have argued in the previous section that one may have a very sharp p values [$\text{sinc}(x)\text{sinc}(x)$ becomes very sharp at $x=0$ for high n] and at the same time a very sharp x resolution i.e. little effect from the wavefunction length spread associated with p . For a free quantum particle $\exp(ipx)$, p has a constant value at each x and one may associate this with a classical particle following $x = (p/m) t$. There is still a wavelength present proportional to $1/p$, but

it is not manifest unless the particle interacts in some manner and tries to set up a potential impulse field, based on its wavelength (two slit interference) or a set of wavelengths due to $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ forming from impulse hits with a potential $V(x)$.

Question of Entropy

One might argue that a classical bound particle is isentropic as its motion is reversible and there is no heat exchange. As a result it obeys Newtonian mechanics, a nonstatistical theory (without friction) at least on the surface.

For a quantum particle in a box with infinite potential walls it is interesting to examine the entropy which we have argued in previous notes should be:

$$\sum_{p, x} P(p \text{ and } x) \ln[P(p \text{ and } x)] \quad ((5))$$

For a classical particle $P(p \text{ and } x) = P(p)P(x)$, but for a quantum particle for a bound state:

$P(p) = a(p)a(p)$ and $P(x) = W(x)W(x)$ where $W(x) = \sum_p a(p) \exp(ipx)$ is the wavefunction. We use

$$P(p/x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) / W(x) = P(p \text{ and } x) / P(x) \text{ so } P(p \text{ and } x) = a(p) \exp(ipx) W(x)$$

If $a(p) = a(-p)$ then we find that:

$$\text{Entropy} = \sum_x W(x)W(x) \ln[WW] + \sum_p a(p)a(p) \ln[a(p)a(p)] \quad ((6))$$

Thus one must add the momentum and spatial entropies. For a particle in a box with infinite potential walls:

Spatial entropy = $\ln[C_1 L]$ This does not depend on n , but is L dependent and C_1 is a constant.

$$\text{Momentum entropy} = \ln(1/L) + \text{function}(n) \quad ((7))$$

The function of n becomes independent of n as $n \rightarrow \infty$ i.e. as the $\text{sinc}(x)\text{sinc}(x)$ function becomes sharper and sharper about $p = n \cdot 3.14/L$. Thus each energy level of a particle in a box with an infinite potential has an entropy based on n , but it approaches a constant in the classical limit. We argue that this is important for creating "classical mechanics" from the high n limit of quantum mechanics. There is no entropy in the high n limit and so classical mechanics is no longer the statistical theory (linked to entropy) that bound state quantum mechanics is.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one may obtain classical mechanics from the high n limit of a quantum bound solution for a particle in a box with infinite walls. We note that bound state

quantum mechanics is an equilibrium statistical theory which removes time from the picture. It involves complex probabilities because momenta are constantly changing due to stochastic impulse hits (with no time reversal balance) from a potential $V(x) = \sum_k V_k \exp(ikx)$. Furthermore there is a spatial nonlocality associated with each particle momentum state i.e. the wavelength. We argue that a quantum particle tries to establish a kind of impulse potential field which is in balance with $V(x)$ through $E_n = KE(x) + V(x)$. At this point, bound state quantum mechanics is very different from classical mechanics. In the high energy (high n limit), spatial resolution becomes very sharp i.e. the wavelength is no longer introducing much nonlocality and $a(p)$ proportional to $\text{sinc}(x)\text{sinc}(x)$ is sharply peaked at $p = 3.14n/L$ a single value of momentum. We argue that this allows for one to suggest a classical theory in which one knows $x(t)$ and follows a particle in time. Examining entropy shows that spatial entropy + momentum entropy is L independent and becomes n independent for $n \rightarrow \infty$. Thus in the very high n limit there is no longer any entropy and one has a nonstatistical theory i.e. classical mechanics. One must, however, "pull" out forward and backward motion contained in the equilibrium solution in order to see a classical particle move forward in one interval in time and then backwards in another. This does not automatically appear from bound quantum mechanics because it has removed time i.e. uses $\exp(-iEt)$.

Reference

1. Majernik, Vladimir; Richterek, Lukas (1997-12-01). "[Entropic uncertainty relations for the infinite well](#)". J. Phys. A. 30 (4): L49. [Bibcode:1997JPhA...30L..49M](#). [doi:10.1088/0305-4470/30/4/002](#).
2. https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Particle_in_a_box